

Pragmatics of Shared Beliefs in Spousal Conflict Resolution Proceedings

by

Temidayo Olutimayin-neil Orunmbe oluneilmbe@gmail.com

Ezekiel Opeyemi Olajimbiti opebukola56@gmail.com

Amos Awobi amos.awobi@fulokoja.edu.ng

Department of English and Literary Studies, Federal University Lokoja

Abstract

This paper examines the pragmatics of shared beliefs held by interactants in the resolution proceedings on spousal disputes at the Justice Court, Nigeria. The data consist of twenty downloaded videos from the YouTube account of the Justice Court, Nigeria, transcribed using Jefferson's transcription notations. The study draws insights from Odebunmi's (2006) model of mutual contextual beliefs and Clark's (1996) model of common grounds for data analysis. The findings show three categories of shared beliefs: shared socio-cultural beliefs on marital practices, shared knowledge of marital responsibilities, and shared knowledge of marital unfaithfulness; characterised by affirmative, validation, contrastive, negation, and reformulation markers. The study demonstrates that justice is culturally legitimate, socially restorative, and linguistically inclusive, thereby enhancing both the credibility of the justice system and the sustainability of conflict resolutions.

Keywords: Contextual Beliefs, Resolution Proceedings, Spousal Conflict, Common Grounds and Pragmatics

Introduction

Spousal conflict is a pervasive phenomenon across cultures, and the ways in which such disputes are resolved reflect not only legal frameworks but also deep-rooted socio-cultural, pragmatic, and discursive traditions. According to records of the Justice Court on their YouTube account, Nigeria's ADR reality series The Justice Court runs a high-volume YouTube docket of spousal disputes (access, upkeep, paternity, infidelity) content optimized for sharing and commentary, which normalizes public airing of marital grievances. In contemporary judicial and quasi-judicial settings, particularly in Nigeria, alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms such as mediation and arbitration have gained traction due to their less adversarial nature and their focus on reconciliation, emotional healing, and familial stability (Adekanye, 2024). The Justice Court, Nigeria exemplifies such a mechanism, operating within a courtroom structure but deploying mediation-like strategies aimed at settling disputes amicably. Language plays a crucial role in the administration of justice with regards to conflict resolution. It serves as the medium through which legal arguments are articulated, evidences are presented, and judicial decisions are delivered.

In Nigeria, a multilingual and multicultural society with over 500 indigenous languages (Ayeomoni, 2012 and Omachonu, 2018), the use of language in court proceedings is of paramount importance. It is then of

great importance to consider the role of language as used in the court/alternative dispute resolution (ADR) sessions. So, by grounding resolutions in shared socio-cultural beliefs, the court ensures that decisions resonate with the disputants' values and expectations. This enhances the perception of fairness, legitimacy, and social acceptability of rulings, thereby strengthening trust in the justice system. The study shows that shared beliefs (e.g., tolerance, co-parenting, spousal responsibilities) create a common ground where the judge can mediate. This aligns with restorative rather than purely punitive justice, aiming at repairing relationships and reintegrating parties into peaceful coexistence.

These beliefs play a vital role in shaping courtroom interactions, framing arguments, and ultimately guiding judicial outcomes. In conflict resolution, particularly in domestic contexts, such shared beliefs are pivotal for creating what Clark (1996) calls common ground; a set of presupposed or acknowledged understandings that speakers assume are jointly held. These beliefs are often unspoken but become visible in pragmatic choices: affirmations, negations, reformulations, and validations that either confirm or deny mutual understanding. They constitute the interpretive and ideological base upon which judges and disputants align their discourse in search of resolution (Raifu et al, 2020).

Therefore, within the Nigerian spousal context, beliefs about marriage, responsibility, fidelity, parenting, and gender roles are not only culturally constructed but are frequently shared across participants (litigants, mediators, and audience). These beliefs are socio-pragmatic tools that help participants justify actions, attribute blame, negotiate repair, or resist accusations. For example, beliefs that position men as breadwinners and women as homemakers (or the converse, in modern urban settings) inform how responsibility and failure are linguistically constructed.

Despite the significant role of such shared beliefs in spousal conflict resolution, relatively little scholarly attention has been paid to their discursive and pragmatic deployment in legal or pseudo-legal settings. Previous studies on adjudicatory and conflict resolution in discourse analysis and pragmatics have examined institutional talk (Drew & Heritage, 1992), courtroom interaction (Gibbons, 2003), Unuabonah (2016), Ajayi et al (2021) but fewer studies have focused on the interactive pragmatics of spousal dispute resolution in Nigerian courts. Furthermore, while sociolinguistic studies have explored gendered discourse (Eckert & McConnell-Ginet, 2003) and marital communication (Tannen, 1990), they often lack a focus on institutionalized conflict mediation, where shared cultural and contextual knowledge becomes a discursive battleground. This study thus fills a gap by examining how shared beliefs are leveraged on in real-life spousal dispute proceedings in the Justice Court.

Literature Review

Spousal conflict is perceived as a global phenomenon as it is not restricted to a particular people, generation, colour or race; but its manifestation in each community and marriage is context specific. The phenomenon of spousal conflict has attracted scholarly attention from various perspectives such as sociology; Amadi and Amadi (2014), Gottman (1994), Osarenren (2013), Fincham and Beach (1999), De Bruyne and Greef (2000), law; Oluwatofarati (2023) and Izunwa (2015), family health and psychology; (Singh and Srivastava; 2023), religion (faith and beliefs); (Ottuh 2013, Chukwuma 2020) and linguistics; (Mojaye 2014, Li and

Wu 2023 and Olorungbemi, 2024). Most of these studies did not fill the gap of language use in spousal conflict resolution proceedings of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) sessions.

While the studies from the disposition of law, religion, sociology and psychology have considered spousal conflict resolution by looking at the guides to mediation, coping methods, health and mental effects, the current study examines how language is used thereby highlighting certain beliefs in the spousal conflict resolution proceedings. The method adopted in the previous studies on marital conflicts resolutions or reconciliations as the case may be, has been through application of questionnaire, survey, quantitative, statistical review of court records or interviews of parties involved (or witnesses). These approaches did not sufficiently account for how language is used in spousal conflict resolution because the data gathered were not treated in context, so the principles and theories of pragmatics that can be put to use were not brought into perspective.

Olorungbemi (2024) examines a linguistic investigation into spousal conflicts by examining stance-taking and pragmatic strategies in news headlines. In doing this, a close attention was paid to the style of news headlines reportage as to unveil the role the media plays in featuring and relating events regarding marital conflicts. In Olorungbemi (2024), the stance types evident in newspaper headlines on spousal conflicts; the pragmatic strategies employed in the headlines reportage; and the system deployed in establishing stance and pragmatic strategies as to enhance possible interpretations of the news headlines on spousal conflicts were thoroughly discussed. But as closely related and relevant Olorungbemi (2024) is to this current study, a point of divergence is in the theoretical framework (stance-taking and pragmatic strategies), scope of data and sources – print media (newspaper headlines – which reported more on spousal abuse and domestic violence) of 2021 to 2023.

On contextual beliefs, Unuabonah (2016) examines the shared contextual beliefs among participants in the 2008 public hearing on the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Administration in Abuja, Nigeria. Utilizing Odebunmi's (2006) model of context, Unuabonah analyses forty video recordings of the hearing to identify the underlying shared knowledge that guides interactions. The study finds that participants' interactions are informed by a mutual understanding of the hearing's aims and procedures, legal codes concerning land ownership, government involvement, and specific knowledge about Abuja metropolis. These shared beliefs facilitate effective communication and contribute to the procedural dynamics of the quasi-judicial setting. The use of authentic video recordings provided a comprehensive view of real-life interactions and this presents a rich data for the study. The research extended the application of Odebunmi's context model to a new setting, enhancing its relevance in judicial and quasi-judicial environments. The study illuminated the influence of socio-political dynamics in shaping communication within Nigerian public hearings. In a similar way this study is applying the Odebunmi's (2006) models of contextual beliefs to data sourced from recorded videos of proceedings at a TV reality show on ADR.

Olajimbiti (2023) explores the linguistic and cultural dynamics of antenatal classes in selected Nigerian hospitals, focusing on how caregivers and pregnant women engage with shared beliefs in their interactions. The study employs a discourse analytic approach, drawing on models such as Odebunmi's contextual

beliefs, van Dijk's epistemic context, and Fetzer and Fischer's lexical markers, to examine the interplay of language, cultural norms, and shared knowledge in antenatal communication. The study addresses a significant gap in discourse analysis by focusing on antenatal classes in Nigeria, where linguistic and sociocultural factors play a crucial role in healthcare communication. Olajimbite acknowledges that much of the research on antenatal care in Nigeria has focused on health utilization and access (e.g., Adewuyi et al., 2018), and his emphasis on the communicative aspects enriches the field of medical discourse, particularly in a culturally rich context like Nigeria. The combination of Odebunmi's and van Dijk's models to analyze the shared beliefs between caregivers and pregnant women provides a robust framework. The study deftly demonstrates how caregivers use lexical markers to engage pregnant women's prior knowledge, correct misconceptions, and navigate the fine line between traditional beliefs and medical knowledge. This approach is particularly effective in showing how communication in a high-context culture like Nigeria requires sensitivity to both professional medical discourse and the sociocultural realities of the participants. The use of real-life data from antenatal classes, including tape recordings and observational notes, lends the article empirical depth. This study draws insight from the work of Olajimbite (2023) on how the theory of contextual belief is applied to data that are Nigerian context situated.

Theoretical Framework

This study employs two complementary theoretical frameworks: Odebunmi's (2006) model of Mutual Contextual Beliefs (MCBs) and Clark's (1996) model of Common Ground. Odebunmi's model of contextual beliefs is centered on understanding how context influences the interpretation of meaning in language, specifically in African linguistic environments. He modeled two levels of beliefs to be Language level and Situation level. Language level posits that meaning is potentially possible if interactants have access to the same language of communication. The situation level is where "assumptions are held on the basis of interactants' shared code (linguistic and non-linguistic) and experience" (Odebunmi, 2006:28). This level is further subcategorized into;

- i. Shared knowledge of subject/topic; the interactants are expected to have the knowledge of the topic of discussion to a certain degree as to share beliefs. In the instances of spousal conflict resolutions an interactant is not to deviate into discussing profit making and margin.
- ii. Shared knowledge of word of choices, referents and references; the situation level shows beliefs of interactants with regards to the word choices (there are expressions that are expected to be used at a court proceeding like "Your Honour, the appellant, the plaintiff, suite, order and more
- iii. Shared socio-cultural experiences, previous or on-going; in the situation where in the interactants possess similar previous or immediate experiences on socio-cultural grounds that have laid a kind of foundation for what to say and what not to say in the course of interacting either at individual level or group. Here credence is laid on the generally accepted and expected social norms and values to form shared beliefs. It is premised on this situation level that expressions like "Did he pay your bride price?" can make a meaning to the interactants and the audience.

The situation sub-level of Odebunmi (2006) model is used in identifying and categorising the features of shared beliefs. This is because of the socio-cultural elements of the data. Common grounds as a model deal with the shared knowledge, beliefs and assumptions that communication partners rely on to communicate effectively. In the process of communicating an idea, the speaker maintains a view of assumption that the listener shares a knowledge of the discussion owing to antecedents or a degree of information shared on the subject matter. The Clark (1996) common ground is adapted to explicate the how the foundation for understanding, coordination and joint action in communication is attained. Applying these models enables a systematic examination of how disputants and judges at the Justice Court rely on and invoke shared beliefs in constructing arguments, legitimizing claims, assigning responsibility, or advocating resolution. For instance, instances of affirmative markers such as “yes,” “true,” or “exactly,” often signal alignment with communal norms, while negation markers like “no,” “not at all,” or “never” are used to resist or disavow culturally-grounded accusations. Similarly, validation markers and reformulation devices are used by judges to recast issues in culturally legible terms, thus grounding their judgments in shared values rather than abstract legal statutes.

Methodology

The data are downloaded videos of the proceedings from the Justice Court’s YouTube handle (www.youtube.com/@JusticeCourtTV). Jefferson’ transcription notations is used in transcribing the data into the written form as to capture all the linguistic and para-linguistic elements of the conversations. Fifteen (15) episodes were randomly selected from the first quarter of 2022 to the last quarter of 2024 (The period focused on is when the show gained popularity after the initial failure as affected by 2020 COVID-19 lockdown. It was also the time when the ADR sessions recorded more of the spousal conflict resolution proceedings) out of an average of about 40 episodes on spousal conflict resolutions across three years. A random sampling method is adopted (only five (5) spousal discourses from the first quarter of 2022, another five (5) only from the second quarter of 2023 and the last five (5) from the last quarter of 2024). This is to avoid an open-ended scope of data to be sourced and sampled for this study. Also based on the preponderance of spousal conflict resolutions at the ADR, since year 2020 and part of 2021 were affected by the COVID-19 affairs. The physical setting of the court is not in the form of a conventional court but has a similitude, an alternative dispute resolution (ADR) with a presiding judge/mediator, police (doubling as court clerk), a sign language translator, the complainant, defendant, and language interpreter (in case of parties without knowledge in English language), then witnesses and audience. The interactions of the participants, particularly that of the complainants, the defendants and the judge form the core contents of the data. Their interactions which are done without the aid of individual or general counsel (to represent their interest), is seen to demonstrate some linguistic features of contextual beliefs and common grounds. The situation level of Odebunmi’s (2006) is used in categorising the shared beliefs according to the orientation of the issues projected, while Clark’s (1996) is employed in discussion the linguistic realisation of the features of shared beliefs.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Three features of contextual beliefs are identifiable in the dataset based on Odebunmi (2006) model of mutual contextual beliefs. These are shared socio-cultural beliefs on marital practices; shared knowledge on marital unfaithfulness; and the shared knowledge on parental responsibility. These shared features are foregrounded through lexical markers such as reformulation markers, alignment makers, inquisition markers (prompters), validation markers, and affirmative markers.

Shared socio-cultural beliefs on marital practices

Shared socio-cultural beliefs on marital practices are perceived as the collectively held and culturally transmitted understandings, values, and expectations that a community sustains. These are associated with the norms, roles, and obligations within marriage. These beliefs shape how marital unions are formed, maintained, and dissolved, influencing partner selection, gender roles, conflict resolution, and inheritance patterns. In the context of marital practices, such beliefs operate as part of a community's "mutual contextual beliefs" (Odebunmi, 2006), guiding interpersonal expectations and legitimizing marital behaviours within specific socio-cultural frameworks.

In most Nigerian societies, sociocultural beliefs have high degree of influence on marital practices, shaping expectations, roles, and rituals surrounding marriage. In these societies marriage is often viewed as a union of two (2) families (not just the two individuals joined by marriage), with significant family involvement in the process. Some of the common marital practices are spousal tolerance, family involvement, gender roles, co-parenting, co-providing, delegatory/transferred parenting, mutual support, open communication, respect, collaborative decision making, child bearing/rearing, fidelity.

Spousal Tolerance

This refers to the ability of partners in marriage to accommodate and endure each other's imperfections, differences, and behaviours, even when they are challenging or frustrating. This is illustrated in the following excerpt to foreground it as part of the socio-cultural practices that is expected in spousal relationship.

Excerpt 1

Background: This excerpt is from a conflict between Lady-K and A.Y. Lady-K took her marital conflict to the ADR for resolution with the aim of having her marriage back in union.

1. Judge: Lady-K, You are MARRIED to this MAN?
2. Lady-K: YES MA
3. Judge: So? Why have you brought him to court::?
4. Lady-K: Eight and five (0.2) so I told mum I don't know anything about hhh the Ring (.) and she
5. started calling me:: NAMES and also hhh> around March last year I noticed my
6. HUSBAND and the::woman in a:: beer Pal our are:: hhh going out and I tried to call

7. mum's attention (.) She was:: like he cannot DO IT, SO Later he just stopped coming
8. HOME:: HOME I move on so:: one day:: I found him in the woman's shop and I ask::ed
9. we should go:: HOME and he refused until I saw he was no longer hhh at the shop<-
10. Judge: Okay so↓
11. A.Y: Thank you ma okay? The whole thing started COVID TIME when everybody(.) was at
12. HOME hhh(.) on my street:: nobody knows me:: So? When the ONE MILLION BOYS
13. and so! Started coming so? We started doing VIGILANTE(.) so? The WOMAN IN
14. QUESTION has a shop that's where we normally assemble not only me oh::: we are
15. a::bout 10 hhh after the COVID she started telling me:: am Dating this woman and I sa::id
16. NO am not Dating Her and she started using People to monitor me:: (0.2) she too started
17. following a group of Housewives hhh in that:: that street and they will be drinking
18. TROPHY and all kind of things::

The excerpt presents instances of spousal tolerance, especially as demonstrated by Lady-K, the wife, in her response to her husband A.Y's suspected infidelity and general neglect. Spousal tolerance, in this context, refers to a partner's endurance, patience, or acceptance of negative behaviors or circumstances within the marriage, without immediately resorting to separation or confrontation. It may be in the instance of enduring verbal abuse, stabilizing the marriage against all odds, attempting and accepting reconciliation.

A linguistic view into this excerpt accounts for lexical markers of spousal tolerance are the specific words or expressions that reflect endurance, patience, or restrained reactions to a partner's behavior, despite emotional, social, or moral provocations. These markers often appear subtly, embedded in emotionally charged recounts of experiences. Lexical markers are words or expressions that help signal meaning, structure discourse, express attitudes, or indicate thematic focus. They play a key role in shaping the pragmatic and emotional tone of a conversation. "I tried to call mum's attention...". The word "tried" reflects that the speaker sought a way of settling misunderstanding rather than taking a confrontational stance, suggesting restraint and emotional tolerance. Then the option of reaching out to the husband's mother shows the cultural belief of managing issues within the families of the conflicting spouses. Another instance is seen in the use of the expression "I move on" in line... It indicates that speaker chose to keep going with the marriage despite the abandonment by the husband. "Move on" is an expression that implies continuity. The use of first-person pronoun "I" indicates the projection of personal beliefs/convictions and commitment to the marriage.

Some markers are identified in the excerpt above those that help in structuring the interaction, these are "so" in lines 3, 12, 13, and 15, wherein it marks progression or inference; "okay/okay so" in lines 10 and 11 are

used to manage turns or shift topic, which reflect alignment of ideas. An element of politeness manifest in the use of honourific expression of “thank you ma” in line 11 which show the speaker’s respect for the referent. The use of “and” in lines 5 and 6 as coordinating conjunction for narrative progression helps in establishing coherence the narrative.

Lines 13 and 14: “We started doing VIGILANTE” and “Not only me Oh::: we are a::bout 10” project a reformulation marker. Reformulation markers are linguistic devices used to signal a speaker’s intention to rephrase, clarify, or elaborate on a previous statement within a conversation or text. The expression “Not only me oh:::” is supplying more information on the information given in line 13. The speaker accompanied this with another marker of affirmation “we are a::bout 10”. The reformulation is done using negators. The expression “Not only me oh:::” also manifest as validation marker that reinforces that were involved too, and by implication project the speaker’s innocence.

The affirmative expression presupposes that since it is not only him that seat at the beer parlour with the woman, he is not having an affair with the woman his wife is suspecting. The expression in line 15 “I said NO am not dating her” is the use of negation markers “NO” and “am not” (which the standard English is I am not) are employed by the speaker to affirm a defensive expression of not dating another woman. The other instance in which affirmative markers are projected in excerpt one, are in line 2 “YES MA” reflecting a clear, respectful agreement in response of the Judge’s question. In line 10 the judge used “Okay” to acknowledge the information given by the litigant and to indicate the yielding of turn. This use of okay is not implying an end to a conversation or to shot the speaker up. The expression “So” as used by interactants in lines 3, 12 and 13 to indicate shared understanding and continuation of a point, then at other realisation as connection marker (a form of discourse management). It is premised on shared socio-cultural beliefs that the female partner endured the unpleasant experiences in her marriage and these are evident in expressions and choice of words.

Spousal abuse

Spousal abuse occurs when one spouse in the marriage uses physical or non-physical means to control and instill fear in their partner. This can include physical violence like slapping, shoving and punching, or non-physical acts like verbal insults, threats of violence and neglect. It is evident in the excerpt above that in most situations where there is need for spousal tolerance, spousal abuse is hiddenly manifesting in different forms. This issue of spousal abuse is an unhealthy socio-cultural practice that manifest in marriages, to the detriment of the peaceful cohabiting of the partners. The shared experience here may be mutually shared or received. As seen in the analysis below, the female partner is the receiver of the abuse, which agrees with the view of Adekanye (2024).

The lexical markers that illustrate spousal abuse in the excerpt above are what this paper name lexical markers of neglect. Instances of these are accounted for in “He just stooped coming HOME” (line 7). This indicates physical abandonment and emotional neglect. By implication the marriage was experiencing disrupts of emotional stability and mutual responsibilities. Another instance is found in lines 8 and 9; “I found him in the woman’s shop and I ask:::ed we should go::: HOME and he refused”. The refusal to return

home despite a plea implies emotional detachment and neglect of possible psychological effects. “Nobody knows me” (line 12) implies lack of social support, which is often associated with emotional neglect or abusive control that leaves the spouse vulnerable and alienated. A direct denial of the accusation of dating the woman in line 16 “No, am not dating her” accounts for the use of two lexical markers; negation and affirmative markers.

Delegatory/Transferred parenting against Co-parenting and co-providing

Excerpt 2

Background: Excerpt 2 contains a trio interactants, although two of the interactants dominated the conversation. It is about how a father is no longer interested in the marital relationship owing to the financial irresponsibility of the wife and then make plans to take the two minor children to his uncle to have custody and take care of them, while he seeks greener pastures.

9. B-Daddy: I remember there was a time(.) hmm I gave her two hundred and fifty thousand to
10. go and start a new BUSINESS, till now I don't have ACCOUNT of that MONEY
11. (0.2) and I don't see her doing anything(0.3) with the money and I don't see her using
12. the:: CERTIFICATE. SO? The children I have discussed with m y un::cle to please
13. so that(.) the CHILDREN will not suffer hhh SETBACKS. The first one will be
14. going to JSS1 by next session, then the second one is a Lady is in primary one
15. now(.)going to primary two (.hhh) that my uncle should ASSIST me, I will carry the
16. two children? and give to him(0.2) he will be responsible(.) for the:: school FEES
17. Judge: You mean (.) he will be ASSISTING YOU TO BE PAYING-
18. B- Daddy: [YES] he will be responsible for the feeding? School fees?...
48. B-Daddy: hhh okay? Fine that's what am a::bout to say(0.2)<THE plea::d that I gave(.) to my
49. Uncle was to let the children stay with him –
50. Judge: >They can't stay with HIM because their mother is alive, the law will only grant THE
51. CUSTODY of the children for either of parties(.)when they are alive<
52. B- Daddy: [OKAY]
53. Judge: If the two of you are dead?(0.3) a::nd God forbid? hhh so take that OFF your mind –
54. B-Daddy: NOW? that-
55. Judge: = let me tell you another thing (0.3) because of the AGE of the children! > you just

56. mentioned a one year old CHILD now< it will be:: it will take somebody that is utterly
57. responsible to take a one year(.) old CHILD?
58. B-Daddy: = [NO] not a year? The two ...
67. Judge: YOU don't know what that(.) Person is doing but you want to drop your CHILDREN
68. there—
69. B-Daddy: NOT PERMANTELY, in three months or four months hhh if I step-
70. Judge: = Does that shows you are hmm hhh a RESPONSIBLE FATHER? YOU CAN'T TAKE
71. THEM to where you say(.) you are not even sure of what they do?(0.2)(hhh)
72. B-Daddy: But am – ...
105. Judge: AM NOT ASKING YOU, am not concerned a::bout that, all I know(.) is what the
106. LAW says and what you have to do::
105. B- Daddy: = >but I don't have hhh any INCOME NOW
106. Judge: You don't have any income but (0.2) you we::re, you have MONEY to travel to
107. Abuja? Lokoja? There are people you are(.) Living with all over the place(0.2) Do
108. you understand? You have not defaulted in paying bills:: ? You are looking good?
109. Do you understand?
110. B-Daddy: [YES]

It is a shared belief in marital practice that the parties that have come together to have children should both train and provide to meet the needs of these children. In the excerpt below, the common interest of the interactants is the welfare of the children and this forms the centrality of the discussion. The first speaker draws attention to this by stating that he discussed them as to prevent them from suffering setbacks he sought for assistance. The socio-cultural belief of delegated/transferred responsibility of the speaker as seen in his expression “[YES] he will be responsible for the feeding, School fees” which is not in line with the institutionally-based belief that the law holds.

The excerpt demonstrates a clash between the belief in delegated or transferred parenting and the legal and moral expectations of co-parenting and co-providing, which are increasingly emphasized in modern family systems and child welfare discourse. B-Daddy's decision to hand over full responsibility for his children to his uncle (lines 12–16, 49) reflects a delegatory approach to parenting, where extended family members are expected to step in, often due to the father's perceived incapacity—financial or otherwise. This is a cultural norm in many African societies, where kinship networks are traditionally involved in child-rearing.

However, this belief is challenged by the legal system in the excerpt. The phrase “he will be responsible for the school fees, feeding...” shows a full transference of both financial and caregiving roles, bypassing the mother and formal co-parenting responsibility. B-Daddy does not engage in co-parenting or shared financial planning with the children’s mother. Instead, he critiques her for mismanaging funds he gave her to start a business (lines 9–11), and rather than seeking joint responsibility, he unilaterally decides to relocate the children. His statements reveal an avoidance of mutual co-providing, where both parents collaboratively support their children. This reflects a shared belief in male control over financial decision-making and delegation of caregiving rather than shared involvement.

The judge expression manifest alignment marker in “he has tried” and “he is struggling”. Alignment markers are linguistic cues that speakers use to signal their understanding and agreement (or disagreement) with their interactant (conversational partner). Alignment markers show how speakers position themselves in relation to each other and their shared discourse, indicating a level of attitudinal or interactional alignment. These markers of alignment manifest as at word level like “yeah”, “okay”, “well”; and at phrase level like “I mean”, “I see”. They show the alignment of the judge in sharing the belief that the man is not in his favourable financial times. Looking at the participles of the main verbs (tried and struggling), one can infer that the subject had made efforts in the past and is still making efforts to float his family but needs temporary assistance. “Judge: all I know(.) is what the LAW says and what you have to do:: You see:: when you make(.) anything a pri::ority in line, there is always a SOLUTION” especially the father “Judge: You are the man(.) so you organise- So! What else do you have to say pertaining to the welfare of the children?” The expression “you are the man, so you organise” agrees with the latter expression “so you look for a solution to it” the solution in this context is provision to meet the welfare needs of the children. “He has tried”, which is synonymous to “It is obvious he is struggling” in this context, establishes a shared knowledge of the father’s providing ability.

Shared Beliefs (Knowledge) of Marital Unfaithfulness

Marital unfaithfulness, often involving infidelity or adultery, is generally viewed as a breach of trust and commitment within marriage, leading to various negative consequences. Shared beliefs across different contexts includes the idea that it damages marital relationship, causes emotional pain, and have social and even spiritual repercussions. Considered in this study is the shared beliefs on infidelity pointing out lexical markers that projects the beliefs around it either by assumptions, implicatures or presuppositions.

Infidelity

Infidelity in marriage, also known as cheating or adultery, involves a violation of trust where one of the partners engages in emotional or sexual intimacy with someone outside the committed relationship. This can encompass a range of behaviors, including physical affairs, emotional infidelity, or even cyber interactions that betray the agreed-upon boundaries of the marriage. Infidelity can have severe consequences for the relationship, leading to feelings of betrayal, anger, depression, and a breakdown of trust.

Excerpt 3

Background: The excerpt is taken from the narrative of the couple that had conflict from a shared experience of business loss. The frustration from this loss degenerated into marital unfaithfulness and separation.

8. Judge: You are the one(0.2) that brought this CASE?
9. Mimo: = YES my Lord
10. Judge: So! <tell me what is going on>
11. Mimo: ma? MY LORD aah::>it happened since(.) two years a::go now that I lost:: where? Am
12. doing my business (.hhh) my BUSINESS cut fire <So? all my business (0.2) worth
13. MILLIONS of money and I was unable to take care of my family (hhh.) (0.3) hhh my wife?
14. my children and went to her mother side- ...
26. Judge: what do YOU have to say? To what your husband has just narrated now?
27. Blessing: YES MA, my honourable! > what my husband just sa::id was true word(.) When his
28. SHOP got burnt(0.2) he was Jobless? Nothing to write home:: about? He was just there?
29. The LIFE that I found him doing (.) was into chronic drinking? and going about
30. molesting women? ...
42. Not until one Day I came back:: from hawking and I heard voices(.) Take it easy? Take
43. it easy? And I tried to check where the noise is coming from (.) hmmm my honourable
44. Judge hhh (.hhh) I saw my husband on WOMEN on my matrimonial BED and I cannot
45. take it(0.2) and on top of that he ask::ed those Ladies to beat me because I tried to fight
46. them and I called HOME and cannot bare it to the extent hhh (0.2) and am having
47. SUICIDAL thoughts but because of my children I will just change my mind(0.2) and
48. that's how I packed out with my CHILDREN I ran away? For my life hhh (0.10)
49. Judge: MIMO? What she said is it true?
50. Mimo: YES MA (hhh)

The narrative clearly presents infidelity as a grave betrayal of the marriage covenant, especially through the wife's testimony: "I saw my husband on WOMEN on my matrimonial BED..." (line 44). The phrase "my matrimonial bed" symbolically intensifies the act, portraying it not just as adultery but as a defilement of a sacred marital space, which aligns with the shared cultural belief that such spaces are to be respected and

protected. The husband, Mimo, narrates his financial downfall: "...it happened since two years ago now that I lost where am doing my business... all my business worth millions... and I was unable to take care of my family" (lines 11–13). This suggests a cultural script where male financial provision is tied to authority and moral conduct. His failure to provide is indirectly linked to his moral failure (infidelity and substance abuse), which reflects a shared belief that economic emasculation may lead to moral collapse—a dangerous, yet commonly implied social logic.

Blessing's narration details not just the infidelity but violence and humiliation, reinforcing the idea that infidelity is often accompanied by emotional and physical abuse: "...he asked those ladies to beat me because I tried to fight them" (line 45). This reveals a patriarchal entitlement often tied to infidelity, where the husband asserts power not only through unfaithfulness but by mobilizing others to harm the wife, violating both intimacy and safety expectations in marriage. Blessing shares how the betrayal affected her: "I cannot take it... I'm having suicidal thoughts but because of my children..." (lines 45–47). Here, we see the communal expectation of women's endurance in marriage being stretched to the limit. Her statement mirrors a shared belief that women are expected to tolerate hardship, but also highlights the psychological toll such beliefs exert, especially when infidelity is involved. While women are often expected to endure, this act of leaving (particularly with her children) shows a shifting belief system where self-preservation and motherhood override marital endurance. The shared belief here is that a wife may justifiably leave a marriage if her life or sanity is at risk, especially due to infidelity compounded with abuse: "That's how I packed out with my children... I ran away for my life" (line 48). Admission and Lack of Remorse are evident in Mimo's response: "YES MA (hhh)" (line 50). His short and unembellished affirmation confirms the wife's narrative, suggesting either resignation or a normalized view of infidelity. The lack of denial or remorse reflects a gendered permissiveness, common in societies where male infidelity is tolerated or excused, especially when tied to stress or financial hardship.

The underlying values and expectations about fidelity are exposed through the use these lexical markers. The use of honourifics and respect markers (Lexical politeness) "YES my Lord", "ma?", "my honourable Judge". These terms signal deference to authority and reflect a cultural belief in hierarchical respect and decorum, especially in formal or public adjudication of moral transgressions like infidelity. They set a tone of seriousness and legitimacy for the claims being made. Lexical emphasis on loss of status and masculine role can be identified in "I was unable to take care of my family", "my business cut fire", and "SHOP got burnt... he was Jobless? Nothing to write home:: about?". These utterances index a shared belief that a man's inability to provide economically is a precursor to marital instability or a loss of moral grounding. It subtly ties financial failure with the perceived justification or onset of infidelity or moral degeneration. Another marker contained in the excerpt is condemnation, which conveys the condemnation of infidelity, especially when it disrupts the sanctity of the "matrimonial bed"—a symbolic space of loyalty and sanctity. The use of "molesting women" and "on women" indicates a moral lapse, aligning with societal disapproval of promiscuity by a married man. Lexical markers of betrayal and trauma are "I cannot take it", "he ask::ed those Ladies to beat me", "SUICIDAL thoughts", "I packed out with my CHILDREN I ran away? For my

life". These lines reflect emotional and psychological trauma, painting infidelity as not just sexual betrayal, but violence against the spouse and motherhood. There is a shared belief here that infidelity leads to or is accompanied by emotional abuse, and that a wife's tolerance has limits.

Shared Knowledge of Marital Responsibility

Marital responsibility encompasses the duties and obligations that both partners in a marriage are expected to uphold, contributing to the well-being and harmony of the relationship. These responsibilities involve mutual support, communication, financial contributions and shared decision-making, among other things. One of the shared knowledge areas of marital responsibility is the responsibility of providing shelter and keeping custody of the children which proves a high degree of cooperation and welfare for the members of the family. Since the man is the head and leader of the family, he is expected to ensure there is no shortage in this provision.

Excerpt 4

Background: This excerpt reveals a courtroom interaction between a judge and a woman (Vero) centered on marital responsibility and neglect. The lexical markers embedded in Vero's responses provide insight into perceived expectations of spousal duty, caregiving obligations, and financial contribution (a key indices of marital responsibility in socio-cultural contexts).

24.Judge: =>when did you separate with your husband(.)<

25.Vero: This January, last year January?-

26.Judge: so? He is aware of it

27.Vero: Yes, he doesn't want to CONTRIBUTE anything to it, when the problem Started(0.2)he

28. behave asive he don't know > For two years, I carry him here and there(.) hhh even

29. when HE will say get out, get out:: nothing is wrong with you? I will carry him hhh to the

30. hospital? Church? Even native Doctor!-

31.Judge: = wait! What do you do for a living?

32.Vero: I sell stationary? Exercise book?(°) or I have small place hhh I also selling(0.2) so? He refuse

33. to contribute to solving the boy problem and even all the other children (.) Or any of the child

34. that has issue> they will say I caused it that am a WITCH, that I want to waste his INCOME?-

35.Judge: what kind of treatment?

36.Vero: A Professor that my cousin took me to:: if he will be able to treat him (0.2) and he was given::

37. first prescription hhh the boys MEDICAL payment is the problem, the drugs i buy for him(.)

38. every week is five thousand plus.

39. Judge: Is the Boy in court::?

40. Vero: I should have brought him but its looking like the thing(.) Is going to come:: again (0.2) so I

41. don't bring it eh::em even eh::en since I have been here praying let it not start, <At times that

42. thing hhh must happen every week> (0.10)

The orientation of the tone of the interaction in the excerpt 4 above is that of report and inquiry. The speaker Vero is the interactant with the reporting tone while the judge is seen to be throwing questions to gain more information that can put the judge at the space of shared knowledge with the complainant. In projecting these, Vero adopts a generous use of pronouns, especially the first person singular "I" and third person singular "He" and "His". The use of "I" by Vero signals the personal roles and responsibilities carried out in taking care of their children, especially the one that is sick with seizure. "For two years, I carry him here and there... to the hospital? Church? Even native doctor!" (Lines 28–30). These expressions signal physical, emotional, and spiritual caregiving efforts, suggesting Vero internalized the expectation of supporting her sick son through diverse healing systems.

A key theme in Vero's complaint is the lack of financial input from her husband, which she explicitly frames as a form of abandonment: "he doesn't want to CONTRIBUTE anything..." (Line 27) and "He refuse to contribute to solving the boy problem and even all the other children..." (Line 33). These lexical markers: "contribute," "refuse," "problem," reflect economic obligations typically assigned to the husband and frame his inaction as a breach of marital duty. The repeated use of "contribute" stresses expected shared responsibility, especially regarding child welfare. By implication, the financial discourse underscores that economic provision is central to the perceived performance of marital responsibility, particularly from the male spouse. In reporting and referring to the disposition of her husband towards her and the sick child, Vero chose the use of the third person pronoun of "He and His" instead of using words that should reflect the relationship of the parents. This lexical choice can be termed to be deliberate as to express her pain and displeasure to her husband's behaviour and to communicate the deteriorating state of the spousal relationship. These phrases index a normative belief that a wife should go to great lengths to care for her children, even in situations of verbal rejection ("get out, get out:: nothing is wrong with you").

An expression of ambiguity is identified in the sudden switch in line 26 "so? He is aware of it", since the preceding lines (24 and 25) discusses a different idea. The two referents "He" and "It" are the lexical markers projecting the ambiguity – who is the "He" and what is the "it" in this expression. The response of the complainant which is an affirmative one "Yes" in line 27 shows a shared knowledge of the topic of discussion (the health issue of her child). The gap fillers like "hmm, hhh, eh::em" are employed by the complainant to express her emotions and to connect lines of thoughts.

Conclusion

This paper has identified and demonstrated three categories of shared beliefs in spousal conflict resolution proceedings at an ADR court: shared socio-cultural belief on marital practices, shared knowledge of marital

unfaithfulness and shared knowledge of marital responsibility. Shared socio-cultural belief on marital manifest in issues like spousal tolerance, spousal abuse, delegatory/transferred parenting against co-parenting and co-providing orientation are highlighted by lexical markers such as affirmative markers, validation markers and negation markers. Shared beliefs (knowledge) of marital unfaithfulness reflects in the issue of infidelity (which occurred repeatedly in most episodes) is foregrounded by lexical markers like reformulation markers, validation markers and negation markers. While shared knowledge of marital responsibility manifesting in parental obligations and spousal expectations are projected through lexical markers of contrastive markers and negation markers. The study has revealed how the litigants' expressions project their knowledge on the issues argued before the mediator. Through this study insight has been given to how the interactions at the ADR juxtaposes the interphase between the legal system, culture and the society as it reflects how their interplay can better the social affairs of the people.

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